

Wallenberg Syndrome Following Anabolic-Androgenic Steroid Use: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Wallenberg syndrome is a rare ischemic stroke syndrome resulting from infarction in the posterior inferior cerebellar artery (PICA) territory. Anabolic-androgenic steroids (AAS), used frequently in athletic settings, are associated with prothrombotic and vasospastic phenomena that may increase the risk of cerebrovascular events.

Case presentation: We report a case of a 39-year-old male strength coach with no prior medical history, who presented with acute onset of vomiting, singultus, ataxia, and ipsilateral facial hypoesthesia. He had a history of self-administered AAS cycles since the age of 19. MRI revealed a left cerebellar hemisphere infarct, and CT angiography hypoplasia of the left vertebral artery with occlusion of distal segments V3 and V4. Cardioembolic, infectious, and autoimmune etiologies were excluded.

Conclusion: Although causality cannot be definitively established, this case highlights the possible association between chronic anabolic steroid use and posterior circulation ischemic stroke. AAS may induce cerebrovascular risk via vascular remodeling, vasospasm, or thrombosis.

KEYWORDS: Wallenberg syndrome, anabolic-androgenic steroids, ischemic stroke, vertebral artery occlusion, lateral medullary infarct.

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INTRODUCTION

The Wallenberg's syndrome also known dorso-lateral medullary syndrome is produced by infarction of a wedge of lateral medulla posterior to the inferior olivary nucleus and is usually caused by vertebral artery occlusion or posterior

inferior cerebellar artery^{1,2}. Stroke mechanisms responsible for posterior circulation ischaemia and anterior circulation are quite similar. Most common causes of vertebrobasilar ischaemia are, in fact, atherosclerosis, embolism, penetrating small-artery disease and arterial dissection and other less common causes³.

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It typically presents with vertigo, nausea, ipsilateral facial sensory loss, contralateral body hypoalgesia, ataxia, Horner's syndrome, and bulbar symptoms such as dysphagia and dysphonia⁴. Approximately 20% of cerebrovascular events occur in the posterior circulation (vertebrobasilar artery)⁵. The vertebral artery is a branch of the subclavian artery and plays a crucial role in irrigating the posterior region of the cerebral arterial circle. Among the various possible alterations, vertebral artery hypoplasia is a significant variant. The percentage of vertebral artery hypoplasia in the general population is around 11%⁶.

Anabolic-androgenic steroids (AAS) are synthetic derivatives of testosterone widely used by athletes and bodybuilders to enhance performance and muscle mass. Their adverse effects on the cardiovascular system include hypertension, dyslipidemia, left ventricular hypertrophy, vasospasm, and increased thrombotic risk⁷. Several case reports have described AAS-related myocardial infarction and stroke, though most involve the anterior circulation⁸.

The posterior circulation accounts for approximately 20% of ischemic strokes. However, its association with AAS use is underreported. This case describes a young, previously healthy male with a history of chronic AAS use who developed Wallenberg syndrome due to vertebral artery occlusion.

CASE REPORT

A 39-year-old male strength coach from Mexico. He denied cardiovascular risk factors, recent trauma, or infection. The patient reported intermittent self-prescribed use of performance-enhancing substances at ages 19 and 35. The regimens included intramuscular nandrolone, stanozolol, and testosterone at an unknown dose.

The last regimen included 3 cycles with weekly doses of nandrolone 50 mg IM, stanozolol 50 mg IM, and testosterone enanthate 250 mg IM for 3 months with 2-month breaks between each cycle. After completing the fifth cycle and until the onset of the current condition, he reported using clomiphene citrate 50 mg daily, stanozolol 50 mg IM weekly, oxandrolone 10 mg PO daily, and tamoxifen 20 mg daily. human chorionic gonadotropin 2,500 IU for 4 doses.

After three weeks, he experiencing sudden-onset vertigo accompanied by emesis on 2 occasions and singultus. He subsequently presented with holocranial headache exacerbated by movement with partial improvement after the use of analgesics and gait imbalance with leftward lateropulsion.

On physical examination, he was hemodynamically stable. Neurological findings included hypoesthesia in the left hemiface (spino trigeminal tract), absent gag reflex (IX–X), voice changes due to involvement of the ambiguous nucleus in the brainstem, and left-sided ataxic gait. Negative head impulse test, absent nystagmus, positive skew test. Motor system: MRC

(Medical Research Council) grade 5, normal distal and proximal stretch in all 4 limbs. DTRs in biceps, triceps, brachioradialis, patellar and Achilles tendon ++/++++ bilateral. Coordination system: gait with base support range, ataxic, lateralized to the left. Proprioceptive sensitivity not affected. Exteroceptive sensitive corporal not affected. Plantar flexor reflex.

Cranial MRI (T2 and FLAIR sequences) showed hyperintensity in the left caudal cerebellar hemisphere (Fig 1). CT angiography revealed hypoplasia and segmental occlusion of the left vertebral artery (Fig 2).

Transthoracic echocardiograph showed preserved systolic and diastolic function with no thrombi or valvular abnormalities. Holter monitoring ruled out arrhythmias. Autoimmune markers and lipid panel were unremarkable.

Fig 1: Cranial MRI showed hyperintensity in the left caudal cerebellar hemisphere

Fig 2: CT angiography: hypoplasia and segmental occlusion of the left vertebral artery V3–V4

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates an atypical cerebrovascular presentation in a young, otherwise healthy adult, potentially linked to long-term anabolic steroid use. Wallenberg syndrome is usually secondary to atherothrombotic occlusion of the vertebral artery or PICA, but in young patients without conventional risk factors, alternative mechanisms such as drug-induced vasospasm or endothelial injury must be considered.

AAS promote thrombogenicity through several pathways: increased platelet aggregation, decreased fibrinolysis, elevated hematocrit, and endothelial dysfunction⁹. Observational studies have documented an increased risk of

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cardiovascular disease in AAS users, including myocardial infarction, venous thromboembolism, and, although less frequently, ischemic stroke^{10 11}.

Anatomical variants are not pathologic per se, they may become clinically significant in the setting of vascular stress or injury. Emerging evidence suggest that vertebral artery hypoplasia may contribute to posterior circulation ischemic events, especially when other risk factors coexist¹².

CONCLUSION

This case underscores the potential cerebrovascular risks associated with unregulated AAS use in young individuals. Wallenberg syndrome, though rare, should be considered in patients presenting with compatible neurological deficits, particularly when conventional stroke risk factors are absent. A high index of suspicion and thorough drug history are essential in such clinical scenarios. Further research is needed to clarify the causal role of AAS in posterior circulation ischemia.

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